

Effects of Transactional Analysis on Prosocial Behaviour of Senior Secondary School Students in Lagos State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of transactional analysis training on the prosocial behaviour of senior secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria. The primary objective of the study was to enhance prosocial behaviour among senior secondary school students in Lagos State through transactional analysis training. The study adopted a pretest–posttest control group quasi-experimental design. Lagos State comprises three senatorial districts, from which two public senior secondary schools were randomly selected. A total of 120 students (60 males and 60 females) identified with low levels of prosocial behaviour participated in the study. Participants were assigned to either a treatment group or a control group. Data were collected using the Prosocial Behaviour Questionnaire (PBQ). One hypothesis was formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. Data analysis was carried out using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

The analysis revealed a significant main effect of treatment, indicating that transactional analysis training had a positive and statistically significant influence on adolescents' prosocial behaviour in public senior secondary schools. The findings suggest that transactional analysis training is an effective intervention for equipping adolescents with interpersonal skills necessary for improving social relationships and positive interactions within society. It is recommended that transactional analysis training be incorporated into school-based intervention programmes and utilised by teachers, counsellors, psychologists, parents, and other stakeholders concerned with adolescent development.

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Introduction

A person must unavoidably go through adolescence as they mature from childhood to maturity. It is a period of transformation, turning a child into an adult. It marks the transition from infancy to adulthood. This stage, known as pubescence, takes place between the ages of 13 and 19. Teenagers frequently have an inflated view of the circumstances they face and think they can manage anything. Their warped self-image, poor social skills, and lack of positive social behaviours often make it difficult for them to deal with difficult situations. Because of their shortcomings in interpersonal relationships, adolescents have frequently engaged in a variety of antisocial behaviours. (Adepegba, 2023).

Prosocial behaviour, also known as voluntary behaviour, is an intentional effort to help or assist others. It is a psychological idea that encompasses a variety of constructive behaviours. It is related to various aspects of positive development among young people, including educational attainment, contentment with individual accomplishments, self-esteem, social skills, and any action aimed at helping others. It is a healthy human act, such as helping, sharing, cooperating, donating, volunteering, and compliance with laws and socially acceptable behaviours (Lai, Sie, & Shek, 2015; Onyencho & Afolabi, 2018).

Essentially, Olanrewaju and Aliyu (2017) define prosocial behaviour as an act that benefits others, such as adhering to rules, being truthful, or collaborating with others in social settings. It is about doing good things for people, no matter who they are to you. It's similar to helping someone in need, sharing what you have, offering your time and expertise, and collaborating with others to complete a task. Giving blood, for instance, is a prosocial act. It is any activity motivated by compassion and a shared concern for the well and rights of others. Alturas and Ausra (2016) affirmed that a better understanding of overall psychosocial

development during adolescence could only be gained through proper knowledge about prosocial behaviour.

Prosocial behavior is a multifaceted approach to assisting, consoling, giving, and being nice to others, as well as occasionally motivated by pragmatic factors like social standing, the desire for direct or indirect exchange, or allegiance to one's own system of justice. Prosocial behavior is motivated by altruism, albeit the definition of pure altruism is debatable because some people think it belongs in the philosophical rather than the psychological domain. (Sloam-Wilson, 2015). Prosocial behaviour increases gradually over time as a child grows into adolescence, and it is closely linked to the development of moral reasoning, empathy, and the child's growing perception of the world.

Children with prosocial behaviour are more likely to have optimistic self-conceptions and become unselfish. They are not self-centred and are more other-oriented. As it suits their own desires, they dedicate more resources to helping others in need. They have positive peer interactions, are more attractive to their peers, and thus more desirable to their colleagues, which makes them more likely to stay optimistic in a relationship.

In our society, several reasons contribute to antisocial behaviour, and theorists of prosocial behaviour are concerned with how these antisocial behavioural patterns can be controlled. One such way is to stimulate the prosocial behaviour of adolescents through their various predictors. Various researchers, Afolabi (2013), Hine (2013), and Lai, Sie & Shek (2015) have listed different predictors of prosocial behaviour in adolescents, which include altruism, public empathy, morality and emotionality.

Transactional Analysis is a rational approach to analysing and comprehending a person's

behaviour, acquiring knowledge and responsibility. Transactional Analysis (TA) was developed by Berne in 1961 (Nelson-Jones, 1995) as a theory of personality. Berne's central assumption, according to Abdullahi, Deribe, and Kura. (2014) is to consider the internal problems and relationships of an individual, and how people are connected. Berne (1961) defines transactional analysis as the method for studying interactions between individuals. The transactional analysis theory is centred on personality ego situations. There are three classes in these: "parent", "adult" and "child" and how people interact with each other within the three personality ego states.

Transactional Analysis is a method for understanding how people think, communicate about themselves, and interact with others. Whenever people interact, a transaction occurs between their different ego states, where one person sends a message and expects a response. The core idea of transactional analysis theory revolves around the concept of personality and ego states. There are three classes in these: "parent", "adult" and "child". Sakaki and Hassan (2017) confirm that Transactional Analysis is one of the most effective psychological theories for resolving problems in human relationships and enhancing people's happiness.

Transactional Analysis is a technique or intervention used to improve various prosocial behavioural problems among school-age children. For example, Nlamedun, Faleye, and Okoye (2013) investigate the effects of transactional analysis and self-efficacy on enhancing social competence among socially isolated pupils in private primary schools in Ibadan. The treatment helped the target students to overcome their incompetence in interpersonal relationships with peers and others. Durmus, Halil, and Mustafa (2015) used transactional analysis to examine the relationship between ego state, life satisfaction, and prosocial behaviour in university students, finding that both

ego state and life satisfaction significantly predicted students' prosocial behaviour.

The intervention helped students improve their interpersonal relationships in school. The nurturing parent in transactional analysis is the aspect of a person who respects and cares about others, while simultaneously setting boundaries on their actions and offering guidance. The choice of transactional analysis as a therapy in the present study is informed by the reality of prosocial behaviours, which are to be strengthened or enhanced, centred on the individual's capacity to effectively negotiate complex social relationships.

Statement of the Problem

We all hope to live in a perfect world where everything's organised, and everyone acts ethically. However, we're a long way from that ideal because human behaviour has declined. The adolescent' years are often chaotic, leading many adolescents to develop unhealthy relationship patterns and disorders that frequently need professional and psychological help. These behaviours include, but are not limited to, fighting, bullying, disrespect for elders, uncontrolled behaviour, and a lack of concern for others.

In today's society, adolescents often display a lack of consideration and exhibit adverse outcomes for others, regardless of their location, in all nations worldwide, including Nigeria. Literature suggests that a lack of prosocial behaviour is one of the reasons why many teenagers, particularly those in secondary schools, often end up in chaotic circumstances. Numerous studies employing various interventions to improve prosocial behaviour in teenagers have been carried out, with differing degrees of effectiveness. However, the cases of antisocial behaviours among adolescents remain endemic, indicating that there is a need for efforts towards providing necessary treatments.

There is no empirical evidence on the use of transactional analysis training to promote prosocial

behaviour, particularly in adolescents, despite reports that it is a powerful therapy for behavioural modification in secondary school. Against this background, this research work examined the effectiveness of Transactional Analysis (TA) in improving the prosocial behaviour of senior secondary school students in Lagos State.

Purpose of the study.

This study aimed to use transactional analysis training to enhance positive prosocial behaviour among senior secondary students in Lagos State, Nigeria. Thus, sets out to investigate the effectiveness of transactional analysis training on senior secondary school students' prosocial behaviour.

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant main effect of transactional analysis (treatment) on prosocial behaviour among the participants.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a pretest-posttest control group experimental design. There were two rows, consisting of one-treatment strategies: Transactional Analysis Training (TAT) and the control group. The researcher adopted a factorial design because the design accomplishes in one experiment what otherwise might require two or more separate experiments.

Population and Sample

The study population comprised all adolescents in Senior Secondary 2 in Lagos State. The sample consisted of one hundred and twenty (120) senior secondary year two (SS 2) students who were selected by simple random sampling from two randomly selected public secondary schools in the three senatorial districts of the state. A sample of 120 students was chosen through the multi-stage random sampling technique. The first stage involved the use of a stratified random sampling

technique to select two local government areas from the twenty (20) local government areas in the three senatorial districts. This was done by writing the names of the LGAs on pieces of paper of equal size. They were folded equally and dropped into the three bowls, each tagged with the name of a senatorial district. After thoroughly reshuffling the contents of the bowls, the researcher selected one Local Government Area from each bowl. The local government areas selected from this process were Ifako-Ijaye Local Government from Lagos West Senatorial District, Lagos, and Epe Local Government from Lagos East Senatorial District.

The second stage involved selecting a secondary school from each of the selected local government areas using a simple random sampling technique. The same procedure employed in selecting the local government areas was also followed in selecting the two secondary schools.

After obtaining permission from the school authorities of each of the selected schools, the researcher administered the prosocial behaviour questionnaires to all senior secondary school (SS2) students. Only respondents who had low mean scores in each of the selected schools were selected as participants in the study. One school formed the experimental group, while the other formed the control group. The study population comprised the entire Senior Secondary School 2 in the public secondary schools of Lagos State. A total of one hundred and twenty (120) students were randomly selected from two co-educational schools. Their age ranged between fourteen (14) and nineteen (19) years. They were randomly assigned to TA and control. The letters A and B were written on separate slips, which were used to assign participants to the treatment group and the control group.

Instrument for Data Collection

A standardised instrument titled "Prosocial Behaviour Scale" by Afolabi (2013) to measure prosocial tendencies was used to collect data for the

study. The data were analysed using Analysis of Covariance. (ANCOVA). It contains 12 items on a four-point Likert-type instrument with responses ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree. The instrument was used to measure the level of prosocial behaviour of the participants. Sample items on the scale include: “*I enjoy helping others*” and “*When people ask me to help them, I don’t hesitate*”. The developer reported that the scale has a coefficient alpha of between .81 and .89, test-retest reliability of .77, and a split-half reliability coefficient of .72 in a sample of Nigerian undergraduates. $p < .05$) and family relations ($r = .417, p < .05$). This confirms the congruent validity of the scale.

Procedure for Data Collection

The study was carried out in three stages as follows:

- (a): Pre-treatment stage involved a familiarisation visit to the three selected schools, which focused on general introduction, establishment of rapport, as well as administration of Prosocial Behaviour Scale (PBS) to all the SS2 students and also a pretest to determine the baseline score. Also, a simple random sampling procedure was used to select 120 participants.

- (b) The treatment Session: The participants in the experimental group were subjected to eight (8) weeks of treatment programmes. The control group participated in pre and posttest sessions but was given placebo training on English language. The subjects in experimental group were subjected to TA Training. The treatment has eight session of the therapy.
- (c) Post-treatment Session: This is the evaluation stage. At the end of the eight (8) weeks of training, both the experimental and control groups were subjected to a posttest using the same PBC to see the results arising from training.

Method of data analysis

Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to analyse the data and test the hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. The statistical tool was used to investigate the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable and the control group.

Results

1. There is no significant main effect of Transactional Analysis (the treatment) on the prosocial behaviour of adolescents in Lagos State.

Table 1: Main effect of treatment

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	198.391 ^a	4	49.598	1.299	.275	.046
Intercept	979.772	1	979.772	25.655	.000	.193
PBSPRE	76.141	1	76.141	1.994	.161	.018
Treatment	118.149	1	118.149	4.263	.042	.041

Table 1 shows the F-value for the treatment ($F_{(4,1)}=4.263, P<0.05$). It follows that there is a significant main effect of treatments on prosocial behaviour among senior secondary school students in Lagos State. The partial eta

square, 0.041, which represents the effect size, is a small value, indicating that although the effect is statistically significant, it is relatively small. The chart below shows the more effective treatment.

Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: PBSPRE = 37.04

The chart shows the same value for both the control and transactional groups. This is because the values are to the nearest whole number. The transactional group is higher by specific decimal values, and that is what the chart is showing. It follows, therefore, that the transactional group is better in effect than the control group

Discussion of Findings

The results of the first hypothesis indicate that there was no significant main effect of transactional analysis training (treatment) on the prosocial behaviour of adolescents. Table 1 shows the F-value for the treatment ($F_{(4,1)} = 4.263$, $P < 0.05$). It follows that there is a significant main effect of treatments on prosocial behaviour among senior secondary school students in Lagos State. The partial eta square (0.001), which determines the effect size, is tiny, confirming the insignificant effect. According to the results of the analysis, presented in Table 1, this hypothesis could not be upheld. It was found that the treatment packages, which are transactional Analysis, had significant effects on the participants' prosocial behaviour.

The participants in the experimental group performed better than those in the control group. The reason for this is mainly because the participants in the experimental group were exposed to the intervention programme. Whereas the participants in the control group were not given any form of treatment, but rather were engaged in activities that had no relevance to what the other participants were exposed to. This means that transactional analysis training had a significant effect on the adolescents, as evident in the posttest scores of prosocial behaviour of the experimental groups. The plausible explanation for this finding is that the intervention (TA) enabled the participants to know themselves, show concern about the way their relationships are with others, set achievable targets for themselves and manage their lives, leading to enhanced prosocial behaviours.

Transactional Analysis is a therapy that assists adolescents to have healthy, intimate and honest relationships towards reducing their stresses and those of others and to enjoy life better. The

adolescents exposed to the treatment group were able to achieve mastery of their environment, improve their personal relationship and communication skills, understand their behaviour, and acquire knowledge and responsibilities.

These findings agree with the conclusion of Womiloju (2015) that participants in the transactional analysis training programme enjoyed a high level of improvement in their social relationships as compared to those in the control group. This result is also consistent with Akintunde (2017), who found that transactional analysis is significant in improving social withdrawal behaviour among adolescents in Nigeria. This finding also corroborates the results of the work of Adimora (2021) on the Effect of Transactional Analysis in Enhancing Secondary School Students' Self-Esteem in Enugu North Local Government Area, Enugu State, Nigeria. It was also in agreement with Badejo et al. in a study that found transactional analysis to be helpful in reducing the psychosocial challenges faced by secondary school adolescents.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effectiveness of Transactional Analysis (SST) on the prosocial behaviours of adolescents in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study aimed to assess the extent to which adolescents in senior secondary school would benefit from developing a sound personality, maintaining good relationships, and receiving sound social support in their day-to-day activities through social skills training strategies. It also went further to examine if gender would have moderating effects on the outcome of the study. From the study, it is evident that adolescents exhibit numerous disapproved behaviours and are unable to initiate friendly relationships, do not understand and respect social norms, find it difficult to help, assist, share things with, and accept others, have cold feelings towards others, and struggle with communicating with others.

Many of these are evident in their relationships with parents at home, teachers, and peers in school. The results have shown that the packages of treatment can be used as proper tools to provide adolescents with the requisite skills to promote successful relationships with others and be good to people around without expecting rewards in return. Thus, through the acquisition of appropriate social and communication skills, their prosocial behaviours became enhanced

Recommendations

As a result of these findings and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are made:

- The introduction of Transactional Analysis Training should start from later childhood to enable adolescents to grow with it, be versed in it and develop the required skills for effective relationships.
- The government should make the provision of professional school counsellors mandatory as a matter of urgency in all public and private schools, in line with the provision of the National Policy on Education.
- Trans are important skills because they are the foundation of all other skills that young people need to succeed in life. Hence, more scientific research must be encouraged and promoted to facilitate success in both academic and social learning of adolescents.
- Experts in counselling and educational psychology should intensify efforts to organise seminars and conferences on the implications of these interventions as effective measures in enhancing prosocial behaviour among adolescents in secondary schools. Students should be encouraged to develop and/or engage in school volunteer service groups.

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